

**SPORT EVENT TOURISM AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PERSPECTIVES
IN DA NANG CITY**

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Abstract

The growth in sport event tourism towards sustainable development has brought some desirable benefits in many destinations, however it can also contribute to over-tourism, which is disadvantageous. Relatively little research has been conducted on the sport event's role in achieving sustainable tourism. The capacity, resources, innovation and engaging a range of key stakeholders, various ways in which events have been considered and operations as green ones. From secondary data sources, the paper explores contemporary challenges that Da Nang's tourism industry acknowledges the importance of sport events, then concludes with an analysis of future research to formulate and implement tourism policies in sustainable tourism development.

Key words: Sport Event, Sustainable Tourism, Challenges, Da Nang City

Introduction

There is a growing recognition of the rapidly increasing importance of sustainability, sustainable tourism, and the concerns for the impacts of non-green tourism events upon tourism patterns and practices (Orefice, C., and Nyarko, N., 2021). Events of various sizes are considered as tourism assets for localities, countries, and regions (Getz, D., 2008) and are seen as having the potential to mitigate the negative impacts of these events at tourist destinations. In recent years, sport events in the light of sustainable tourism development have been held in localities with different scopes, sizes, and meanings, attracting attention and participation significantly by locals, domestic and international tourists, businesses, and stakeholders.

Sustainable tourism is considered the most suitable approach through efforts aiming at green growth and sustainable development in its country, region or local jurisdiction in order to adapt to the reality of climate change, maintain essential ecological processes, minimize impacts on the environment from tourism activities, harmonize economic goals with conservation and promotion of national and regional cultural identities (Hardy, A., Beeton, R. J., and Pearson, L., 2002; Scott, D., 2021). Scholars identified that the tourism events are not always positive but also negative, affecting the economy, socio-culture, and the environment across the triple bottom line (Nawarathna, D. B., and Arachchi, R. S. S. W., 2021; Orefice, C., and Nyarko, N., 2021). Previously, Carlsen, J., and Taylor, A. (2003) mentioned that green elements in the event industry are crucial and important drivers of sustainable tourism that are preferable in implementing planning and organizing any events. It is also associated with emerging products and services and always meets the needs of customers with tourism products and services that do not harm the environment (Merli, R., Preziosi, M., Acampora, A., Lucchetti, M. C., and Ali, F., 2019).

In Da Nang city, since 2008, the city government of Da Nang has issued the project "Building Da Nang - an environmental city", aiming to become the "Green City", internationally standardized by Worldwide Fund For Nature (WWF). In 2018, Da Nang was honoured to become the National Green City of Vietnam, to receive the title of National Capital 2018 by the Worldwide Fund for Nature (WWF)'s One Planet City Challenge programme. Along with the goal of "Green City", with favourable natural conditions, the development of sustainable tourism in Da Nang is being

considered as the right choice of local authorities and investors when approaching natural resources (mountain, marine-based tourism) for the city's sustainable development.

From 2016, developing sport events in tourism activities in the direction of sustainable growth of Da Nang city has been facing challenges, arising potential shortcomings. Adopting the theoretical perspectives, secondary data was derived from academic sources, including key texts and research journal articles in sport event concept, sustainable tourism and report data period 2018- 2021 of Danang tourism, thus aims to: (1) Clarifying the sport event concept associated with sustainable tourism; (2) Analysing the current state, challenges in organizing events towards the goals of sustainability; (3) Suggesting solutions and policy implications with orientations in event management towards sustainable tourism in general and in Da Nang in particular.

2. Sport events in sustainable tourism development

Sustainable development is a process that plays an essential role in the current state of the world because it addresses solutions for social and environmental problems. Sustainability concept has long focused on the relationship between economy and ecology, with more weight given to the latter as a critique of capitalist exploitation of the environment (Kirsch, 2010). As a structural vector of today's society, sport plays an unavoidable role as a promoter of a more sustainable future (UN, 2015). The way in which sport is conceived is decisive for the inclusion/exclusion of a wide range of activities (Martins, R., Pereira, E., Rosado, A., and Mascarenhas, M., 2021). Sustainable behaviors, specifically addressing the action of the individual sport actors (i.e., practitioners, spectators and residents) are used as outcome variables to emphasize people's behavioral intentions to protect the human-social capital and environmental resources. Active sport event participation is often referred to as sport event consumption that targets individuals who are actively involved with a sport (i.e., running) sustainable development allows future generations to satisfy their needs and desires properly. The integration of sport and sustainable development can positively enhance social and environmental outcomes to encourage a sustainable future (Triantafyllidis, S. and Darvin, L., 2021).

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) (2009) also clarified some types of green event as a planned, coordinated, implemented event that reduces the negative impact on the environment and leaves a positive legacy for the host community. UNEP has initiated a programme that aims at integrating environmental sustainability into decision making in the tourism industry and into consumers' purchasing choices, by disseminating technical know-how and building business networks to catalyse 'sustainability' in the tourism sector. In particular, green practices in terms of waste reduction/ minimizing strategies, recycling initiatives, water protection, energy management, pollution reduction, zero emissions, water savings, material use reduction, material life cycle assessment, and toxicity reduction are among the various ones in event management and sustainable tourism. In particular, the UN's call to consider the fundamental societal changes required to stem the tide of climate change, and the importance of the environment in matters of development should resonate with critical scholars of sport. Indeed, in recent years, sport has already been cast as an engine of sustainable development. A case in point here is the UN's inclusion of sport in the SDGs. Through Article 37 of the SDGs, the UN identified sport as an "important enabler of sustainable development" (UN, 2015, para. 37) and recognized sport's ability to "promote awareness towards climate protection and stimulate enhanced community response for local environmental preservation," while acting as a tool for "teaching children and youth about environmental sustainability and climate change" (Millington, R., Giles, A. R., van Luijk, N., and Hayhurst, L. M, 2021).

Recent research has taken sport events in the perspectives of "Greening" events that have become an optimal and inevitable choice in related industries and fields. Holmes, K., Hughes, M., Mair, J., and Carlsen, J. (2015) as it is believed that green practices in sport events are important for participating organizations and businesses successfully; for example, when participating in the event bidding process, hosting mega-sporting events. Green practices will help maintain bidding success and help homeowners earn more sponsors (FISA, 2013) since securing a major event bid

for the next year in a row will be more difficult than the process. its bidding. Moreover, green practices are also important to maintain effective business operations in the long term and develop an organization's green culture (Chiu, L. K., Ramely, A., and Abdul Wafi, A., 2020). The implementation of green events brings many positive impacts to the environment and to the local community, aiming at the main sustainable goals in reducing the negative impacts on the community's natural habitat; pursuing global environmental sustainability goals; promoting programs that promote sustainable living; while ensuring economic efficiency, social justice, and environmental integrity. This green practice relates to sustainable tourism and also gives a good brand image to the destination, for which it has been recognized as a "new tourism" (Chiu, L. K., Ramely, A., and Abdul Wafi, A., 2020). Communities can benefit economically, in terms of environmental health, reduced stress on public infrastructure, and long-term benefits of the facilities. More importantly and interestingly, the study by Rittichainuwat, B., and Mair, J. (2012) shows that the majority of event participants prefer to participate in green events, even though the event fees (non-green) are cheaper than green events.

In order to promote and use relevant resources, stakeholders in the organizational plan must ensure the following principles: (1) traffic management, (2) waste management, (3) water management, (4) energy saving, (5) green shopping, and (6) green promotion (Ramely, A., Talib, M. F. A., Radha, J. Z. R. R. R., and Mokhtar, M. F., 2021). For example, green practices can include using cyberspace in issuing invitations and conducting event promotion, green communication, using environmentally friendly materials, or simply reducing energy consumption during the event. In particular, with the 4.0 revolution, technology plays a role in innovation in green event organization, through the application of technology in the event organization stages to reduce the use of resources and waste (Türkmendağ, T., and Türkmendağ, Z., 2022).

Participants should include regulatory authorities, organizations, businesses, community involvement and visitors. Simultaneous involvement of government agencies and businesses is a necessity for a tourist-friendly destination (Anuar, A. N. A., Ahmed, H., Jusoh, H., and Hussain, M. Y., 2012). Accordingly, the public sector will contribute to the development of the policy system, the transport system (road, waterway and air), and the local identity (such as traditional festivals and monuments, history), and infrastructure (such as lighting and landscaping) at the destination. Meanwhile, the private sector will be responsible for tourism investment such as amenities, accommodation and food services, types of tourism and human resource supply. Organizations and businesses, whether or not they coordinate with management agencies in organizing events, must also be responsible for the impacts of the event on the environment (Moise, D., and Macovei, O. I., 2014). The local community that organizes the event is seen as an important presence as their participation increases the specific values of the locality (Hannam, K., and Halewood, C., 2006). Meanwhile, visitors are the main target and attraction of any tourism activity.

Combining the theories about the above events, it can be seen that the studies focusing on sustainable tourism development identify the theory of sport events that promote the sustainable tourism development of 4 core values: (1) the Innovation development (2) Conservation; (3) Education (4) Visitor satisfaction: It is the result of combining the development of elements of ecotourism, sustainable development, fair trade, renewable energy, corporate social responsibility (CSR) and greening practices (Merli, R., Preziosi, M., Acampora, A., Lucchetti, M. C., and Ali, F., 2019; Goldblatt, J., 2010).

3. Sport Events and Sustainable Tourism Development In Da Nang City

Da Nang tourism has had rapid development and has been honoured with many international awards and titles such as 'Asia's Leading Festival & Event Destination' at the World Travel Awards (WTA) Asia & Australasia Gala Ceremony 2016 held in the city. TripAdvisor has revealed the winners of the 2020 Travellers' Choice Destination awards; the US travel booking, and review website has named Da Nang as one of its top 10 trending destinations for 2020. In the process of developing tourism into a spearhead and sustainable economic sector, the city focuses on

restoring tourism activities after the impact of Covid-19, keeping Danang safe and a green destination. The city has implemented a tourism development, oriented planning with a focus along the Son Tra - Ngu Hanh Son coast, along the Da Nang bay, the hill area, and the Son Tra Peninsula to effectively use the natural resources of the city. In particular, natural water surface, historical and cultural relics, natural landscape, and biodiversity have formed many eco-tourist zones (typically ecotourism sites such as: Suoi Hoa ecotourism area, Ngam Doi ecotourism area, Nui Than Tai ecotourism area, Hoa Phu Thanh ecotourism area, Tien Sa ecotourism area), creating a variety of tourism products associated with nature and the environment, providing many options for tourists, tourism activities and events.

Tourism potentials and green space: Da Nang city has diverse, rich, and high-value tourism resources with a system of seas, mountains, rivers, lakes, hills, streams, ravines, waterfalls, a large agricultural and rural space, and many cultural relics, historical culture, and valuable art architecture. Up to now, the city has 02 special national relics, 17 national-level relics, and 65 city-level relics. There have been 06 local intangible cultural heritages recognized by the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism and included in the list of National Intangible Cultural Heritage, 06 artifacts are kept at the Museum of Sculpture in which Cham carvings are recognized as a national treasure. Based on the review and assessment, it is estimated that among 6 districts of Danang, there are 114 cultural and natural resources that are potentially valuable for tourism from Hoà Vang rural district (49 resources), 11 resources in Lien Chieu district, 11 resources in Son Tra district, 10 resources in Ngu Hanh Son district, 15 resources in Hai Chau district, 6 resources in Thanh Khe district, 10 resources in Cam Le district (there are also 02 Other intangible cultural resources are Tuong Art and Bai Choi Art).

Regarding green space, as of 2017, the greening area in Da Nang reached 84,458.7 hectares, accounting for 65.73% of the city's area. Much of Da Nang's mainstream green space is made up of forests to the west of the city and an area of Son Tra Peninsula. The rest is the urban area and the city's infrastructure (Do, D. T., Huang, J., Cheng, Y., and Truong, T. C. T., 2018).

Tourism growth: The average growth rate of total tourism revenue in the period 2016-2019 reached 24.6%, of which, in 2016 it was 23.72%, by 2019 it will be 31.4% (of which the direct contribution is 13%). 7%, spill over contribution to other sectors and fields is 17.7%). Tourism also created many jobs with 50,963 employees in 2019, an increase of 2.2 times compared to 2016 (Nhat Ha, 2022). The city's tourism industry has also been honoured, receiving many international awards such as Asia's Leading Festival Event Destination (2016), topping the Top 10 Global Destinations in 2020.

In 2020, the outbreak of the Covid-19 epidemic has had a strong impact on the tourism development of Vietnam in general and of Da Nang city in particular. Total revenue of the city's accommodation and travel services in 2020 is estimated at VND 3,705.3 billion, down 57.8% over the same period in 2019 (Department of General Planning, 2020). In 2021, revenue from accommodation and travel services is estimated at 2,505 billion VND, down 37.7% compared to 2020 (Hong Quan, 2022).

Tourist arrivals: The average growth rate of tourists to Da Nang in the period 2016-2019 reached 16.73%. In 2019, the total number of visitors to Da Nang reached 8.6 million, of which, international visitors were estimated at 3.5 million. Total tourism revenue is estimated at 30,973 billion VND. Da Nang has 35 international routes with a frequency of 496 flights/week and 10 domestic routes to the city with a frequency of 662 flights/week.

In 2020, due to the impact of the Covid-19 epidemic and epidemic prevention measures, the total number of visitors to accommodation establishments serving in November 2020 was estimated at 221,209 arrivals, down 67.6% over the same period in 2019, of which International visitors were estimated at 12,207 arrivals, down 95.3%, domestic tourists were estimated at 209,002 arrivals, down 50.9%. Accumulated in the first 11 months of 2020, the total number of guests served by accommodation establishments is estimated at 2,434.3 thousand turns, decrease

63.9% over the same period in 2019; in which, international visitors were estimated at 686.2 thousand arrivals, down 73.8%, domestic tourists were estimated at 1,748.1 thousand arrivals, down 57.6%. From May to 2021, tourism activities will continue to be affected due to the COVID-19 epidemic, the number of visitors has decreased significantly, severely affecting tourism activities in the context that tourism businesses are trying to recover after the pandemic downtime. The total number of visitors to the accommodation establishments reached 1.19 million, down 55% compared to 2020. In which, international visitors reached 105,000, down 85% over the same period; domestic tourists reached 1,085 million arrivals, down 44.2% over the same period; revenue from accommodation and travel services is estimated at 2,505 billion VND, down 37.7% compared to 2020 (Hong Quan, 2022).

The infrastructure: In terms of Parking: Currently, according to the review and survey results in 3 districts of Hai Chau, Thanh Khe, and Son Tra, there are a total of 56 parking lots, including 24 existing public parking lots and 18 parking lots. Current parking for individuals and businesses and 14 spontaneous parking lots invested by the private sector. From 2016 until now, the city has implemented a measure to ban parking on the street on even and odd days in order to limit parking on the street and reduce traffic congestion.

In terms of Power system: The power supply for the loads in the City area is taken from the national grid. Currently, the medium voltage grid has covered the entire area and 100% of households have received electricity from the national grid. Some 22kV roads have been underground, mainly in the main roads and the city center. All roads have been installed with lighting systems to meet the travel and living requirements of the people, in addition, there are decorative lighting systems in some major roads, public areas where people gather. People, tourists, bridges. The existing electricity supply is sufficient for living, production, and business needs. In terms of Water supply system: Currently, the city is using water sources from Yen - Cau Do river system, Cu De river, spring water source (Da stream, Tinh stream, Luong stream), lake water (Hoa Trung lake). The water supply system covers most of the city, basically meeting the needs of daily life, production, tourism business and services. In terms of System of collection and treatment of wastewater and waste: The speed of urbanization in the city is taking place rapidly, the population density and the number of tourists to Da Nang continuously increase (up to the time before the epidemic). COVID-19), resulting in a sudden increase in water demand and discharge volume, putting great pressure on infrastructure for wastewater collection and treatment, and waste collection; The most affected area is the eastern coastal area (in the basin of Son Tra and Ngu Hanh Son districts).

Planned and organized events: As a tourist city, Da Nang city has taken advantage of its resources to organize many tourism events to promote the city's image and attract tourists to experience city tourism activities and events. Events in the city are managed and organized by the local government and called for by many tourism businesses to cooperate. Table 2 lists the city's outstanding tourism events from 2016 to 2022.

Table 2. City's sport event tourism (Year 2016-2022)

Event schedule	Event name	Promoting Event message and goals
Annual event (19-20/3/2022)	Danang International Marathon 2022	The message "Run it, Beat it", <i>the race is not just a place where each individual strives to break his own limits to discover a better version of himself. Running is the starting point of the journey and conquering the race is the beginning of discovery.</i>
Annual event (2018-2)	Opening of sea tourism season	"Sea tourism season": <i>In order to kick off the Da Nang beach tourism season, introduce new activities and services to locals and visitors. At the same time, it contributes to enriching entertainment activities on the occasion of April 30-May 1 and is an auxiliary activity of the Danang International Fireworks Festival. Through the program, it will also propagate to raise public awareness about environmental protection in Son Tra peninsula and beaches sport activities (in 2018).</i>
Annual event (June-July 2019)	Danang International Fireworks Festival 2019	"Cultural tourism events"
Annual event (June 2019)	Danang Summer rendezvous	"Summer rendezvous": <i>Many attractive activities in terms of entertainment, culture, sports, cuisine, and community activities.</i>
March 2019	ABG5 Asian Beach Games	"Beach Games": <i>The combination of sea and sand waving together reflects the strength and strong will of Vietnam and carries a friendly and welcoming message to all sports delegations; represents the solidarity and friendship of the Asian family with the expectation of the successful 5th Asian Beach Games</i>
May 2019	Asian Golf Tourism Congress 2017	"Golf Tourism": <i>For golf destinations to introduce new golf courses, meet partners in the golf industry, hotels work together</i>
June 2019	Danang International Food Festival	"Food Festival": <i>Introducing the typical cuisine of Da Nang to people and visitors, promoting, and promoting tourism on the spot, attracting tourists.</i>
09/5/2021 (cancelled) 08/5/2022	VNG IRONMAN 70.3 Vietnam Competition	IRONMAN: <i>The message "Embracing Challenges" of the season is also a cheer for the resilient strength of domestic athletes in particular and all Vietnamese people in general.</i>

(Source: Tourism reports of Da Nang Tourism Department)

Over the years, being aware of the importance of tourism's impact on the environment, as well as sustainable development and the goal of building an environmental city, many tourism activities and events are geared towards nature, implemented by the city. Various types of tourism are associated with events to raise awareness of marine environmental protection were organized such as the "Clean up Son Tra" program (Coordination with Green Viet - Green Viet Biodiversity Conservation Center) propagandize to raise public awareness on environmental protection, thereby conserving biodiversity and protecting wildlife in Son Tra peninsula, minimizing environmental pollution caused by waste, especially plastic waste. It aims to raise public awareness about environmental protection in Son Tra peninsula and tourist beaches through the event "Opening the sea tourism season". Events in the light of sports events/activities (running, golf, sports associated with marine resources) have also been planned and organized: Marathon event, Asian Beach Games, Golf Tourism Congress Asia.

4. Challenges in the development of sport events for sustainable tourism development in Da Nang city

The risk of ecological environmental deterioration, biodiversity loss, loss of urban landscape quality and value: The planning system is not keeping pace with the rapid urban transformation and especially the urban transformation, lacking the integration of sport space into green urban planning... are inadequacies in the urban planning of Da Nang. According to the United Nations Environment Program - UNEP, the negative impacts on the natural environment from tourism events, including ecosystem, soil structure becoming weak, can affect the environment. natural, noise and light pollution; Consumption of non-renewable resources; Consumption of natural resources; Increase greenhouse gas emissions; increased waste from construction, organization and the number of spectators attending the event.

Limited resources in the infrastructure, environmentally friendly facilities, waste and energy consumption and resource management for the event: The sport event must be held in a place that matches the criteria of the event such as technology or ecological materials. In fact, in the research and evaluation results of impact analysis from event service activities, resources are used in events that can cause negative impacts on the environment: System, flow overcrowded, congested traffic (Hong, M., Li, Z., and Drakeford, B., 2021; Park & Boo, 2010); food waste, dense cooking fumes, excessive use of plastic, cardboard and Styrofoam bags to store and display food these factors can all harm the environment (Laing, J., and Frost, W., 2010).

These issues that need to be considered in relation to sport event also include traffic management and waste management. Traffic often negatively affects the environment through the discharge of vehicles, especially when traffic demand will increase dramatically on event days. Meanwhile, waste is always a part of any event, especially events that attract a large number of people to attend such as sporting events. Therefore, high-performance waste and traffic management measures to reduce emissions during operation should be considered in advance to ensure green factors.

The consensus/participation/commitment of stakeholders: Stakeholders are not always fully aware of the harms of sports event to the environment. It is possible that many participants do not know the importance of sustainable factors to look at and consider and why they have to be conscious of behaviours when participating in the event. Therefore, to ensure the success of a sport event, it is necessary to ensure the agreement of the participants on the purpose of the event, especially the support of the local government to increase the interest of the event and community attention (Ramey, A., Talib, M. F. A., Radha, J. Z. R. R. R., and Mokhtar, M. F., 2021).

Human resource strategy/Policies: A successful green event is demonstrated by the efficiency and effectiveness of using resources, including financial and human resources. Therefore, in the context of sport event organization, organizers need to find employees with the right

qualifications and skills to organize these events. In addition, the organizer needs to organize training, update knowledge, and maintain this number of trained and experienced staff. In addition, financial strategy also needs to be considered. In any event management, sustainable resource management can be achieved through price adjustments that minimize pollution and resource use, such as the use of surcharges and taxes.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

Developing sport events is an opportunity for sustainable development of the tourism industry, which needs to be implemented simultaneously with three economic, political, and cultural pillars that enables promoting local and national tourism images, tourist images of destinations, building brands, creating great leverage for tourism development, economic growth both short and long term. With diverse geographical features, and resources, Da Nang city is suitable for the development of sport tourism events in sustainable tourism development. This event is not only associated with activities with the participation of the local community, but also environment-friendly tourism services are developed at the same time.

With the goals for sustainable tourism development and for "dual goals" in term of "effective prevention and control of the COVID-19 epidemic with socio-economic development, tourism policies have been approached with the motto " Proactive - Adaptive - Flexible" in the new situation in Da Nang city with four main focus: (1) Reducing the intensity of greenhouse gas emissions per GDP; (2) greening economic resources and sectors; (3) greening lifestyles and promoting sustainable consumption; (4) greening the transition on the principles of equality, inclusion, and resilience. To be able to adapt to climate change, Da Nang city needs to focus on the following solutions:

Developing and implementing programme plans, propaganda, promotion, marketing event messages before, during and after the event, preserving the tourism environment, improving community health through sport tourism events. For sports events, it is a must of 1–2-year notice/ plan before the official event takes place in order to have thorough preparation and close coordination between the destination tourism management agency, the sports event organizer sports; effective public-private partnership between tourism management agencies, tourism businesses, sports facilities, and sports training centres. Watt's research since 1998 highlighted the importance of successful event goals when all the different stakeholders reach a consensus on the purpose and benefits of participating in the event. In order to compete in tourism market development, propaganda, and public awareness raising, stakeholders need to have a deep understanding of the benefits and impacts of sport tourism events, from the bidding process to events, promote sponsorship opportunities of prestigious domestic and foreign organizations to ensure success in planning and implementing events in accordance with the green event goals.

Linking-closely associated in mobilizing resources for event development with the central regions, the whole country, the region and the world. It is to strengthen cooperation expansion, mobilize resources with businesses, service providers from service/carrier, accommodation, travel, event organization, forming a chain of links, synergy implements the professionalism and pervasive attraction of green events. At the same time, by mobilizing resources from international organizations and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), the Asia-Pacific Tourism Association (PATA) that participate in major events to ensure that the environment is being protected, in particular UNEP promotes public awareness of the importance of the environment and provides, green practice guidance such as in the Olympic Games, FIFA World Cup. Then, organizing green urban landscape architecture, ensure synchronization of infrastructure conditions, tourist facilities, sports events, ensure security and safety. Prepare infrastructure to serve the large number and needs of event participants as well as visitor satisfaction before, during and after the green event.

Supporting responsible, green practice activities/ education training in events by organizing human resource training classes, training on environmental protection for managers, business

executives, drivers, guides; volunteers; Inspect and examine the observance of regulations on environmental protection, propagate and raise social awareness on environmental protection in tourism; encourage tourists to use and bring eco-friendly or recyclable bags to use while traveling, to tourist attractions; littering, classifying garbage in the right places... in order to create a civilized, friendly and harmonious destination with nature (Trinh, T. T., Ryan, C., & Bui, H. D; 2020).

Develop an education roadmap to provide solutions for waste management at source, integrating this issue in all socio-economic development activities of the city. Departments and related sectors should have a propaganda direction for businesses to find environmentally friendly products to replace plastic products and have policies to encourage businesses to go in the direction of building green businesses, honouring those who do good for the environment.

Encourage and support organizations and individuals in responsible initiatives, innovation development and use of green resources in green tourism types in combination with other tourism models that also include other activities. movement to bring awareness about pollution reduction and efficient use of energy. Supporting policies, including price policies to support, encourage and facilitate the use of green technology and materials for businesses to realize the benefits of deployment. Measures include encouraging tourism products such as sport tourism using environmentally friendly means, such as bicycles, electric cars, cyclos; walking streets, nature-oriented tours to protect the environment, create sustainable livelihoods for local people... are oriented and create a mechanism to make good use of them. Other forms of green tourism such as community learning tourism allow attendees to ride bicycles and use public transport as well as limit smoking on site (Merli, R., Preziosi, M., Acampora, A., Lucchetti, M. C., and Ali, F., 2019), for participants from tourists to indigenous communities to share benefits together (Trinh, T. T., Ryan, C., & Cave, J; 2016), indigenous knowledge, and protection of the ecological environment are promoted through this interactive activity.

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